

A model of the nitride pellet – cladding axial interaction in a fast reactor due to jamming*

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Abstract

In the process of a post-irradiation examination of nitride pins irradiated as part of experimental BN-600 reactor fuel assemblies, a noticeable elongation and a higher ovality of nitride pins cladding were observed as compared with oxide fuel pins. The analysis results suggest that this takes place due to a local mechanical effect fuel pellets have on the cladding. The potential cause for the fuel-cladding thermomechanical interaction is the fuel pellet misalignment, the pellet jamming and cracking as a result of thermal stresses under reactor power rise, and subsequent jamming of large fuel fragments in the cladding. The paper presents the fuel jamming model which assumes the fuel-cladding interaction via an axial force in each calculated radial layer. The axial force is determined from the condition of equilibrium in the radial cladding and fuel cross-section and ensures that the jamming condition (the same growth in axial deformation) is complied with. Jamming is assumed along the entire core height in the presented model version. The presented results of the jamming model verification, based on post-irradiation examination results of the BN-600 EFA-11 (experimental fuel assembly), show that the model allows simulating the fuel pin cladding elongation. The EFA-11 fuel assembly with fuel pins of the BREST-OD-300 reactor type with the cladding made on EP823-Sh ferritic-martensitic steel and nitride uranium-plutonium fuel was irradiated in the BN-600 reactor to the maximum burnup of 9 at.% and the maximum damage dose of 107.6 dpa.

Keywords

mixed nitride uranium-plutonium fuel, jamming, fuel pin, fuel pellet, post-irradiation examination (PIE), elongation, stress-strain state (SSS), model, verification

Introduction

Specific form change of fuel pins with mixed nitride uranium-plutonium fuel is observed in the process of post-irradiation examinations (PIE) of nitride pins, irradiated as part of combined and full-scale experimental assemblies of the BN-600 reactor, which manifests itself in excessive

length and more elliptic cladding as compared to oxide pins (Grachev et al. 2017; Kryukov et al. 2021; Zabudko et al. 2021). An analysis of the PIE results for dimensional changes of fuel pins, taking into account foreign data (Kerrisk et al. 1976; Tanaka et al. 2004; Fromont et al. 2005), make it possible to state that this takes place due to the local mechanical effect of fuel pellets on the cladding.

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The potential cause for the thermomechanical fuel-cladding interaction is misalignment of fuel pellets, their jamming, and pellet cracking as a result of thermal stresses under reactor power increase and further jamming of large-size fuel pieces in the cladding.

One of the objectives pursued in mathematical simulation of the thermomechanical fuel behavior is to predict the parameters of the fuel stress-strain state (SSS), including form change. To do this, it is required to develop models of potential cladding-fuel local interaction. The models being developed are based on experimental results assuming that there are multiple fuel-cladding interaction types:

- axial deformation of the cladding between the locally jammed fuel pellet and the lower fuel column retainer (Likhachev et al. 1975);
- axial deformation under the action of the axial force caused by friction due to accidental fuel pellets displacement (Tutnov and Ylyanov 1987).

A fuel jamming model is proposed in this paper.

Estimation of the fuel pin elongation caused by pellets displacement and/or skewing

The DRAKON code was used for the computational studies, which employs the following approach to calculating the temperature and SSS (stress-strain state) parameters of cylindrical fuel pins (Likhachev and Pupko 1975; Ganina et al. 2018, 2023):

- the core length of the fuel pin is divided axially into N_z sections, small enough for the axial temperature and neutron flux gradients to be neglected; each of N_z axial sections is considered in plane deformation conditions;
- each radial section of fuel and cladding is presented in the form of thin coaxial layers; within each layer, due to it being thin, the temperature, swelling, creep and physical-mechanical properties of the material are assumed to be uniform;
- within one time interval and for each fuel pin axial section, operating and loading factors are calculated: temperature (fuel, gap, cladding), swelling of materials and amount of fission gas release within the length in question;
- a system of equations is solved that describes the cladding and fuel SSS in the R-geometry coordinates (symmetrical problem definition);
- the core length is integrated axially so that to determine the total amount of fission gas released under the cladding in the given time step, as well as new (time-dependent) values of the fuel pin geometric characteristics.

With this approach to the SSS problem solution, it is possible to estimate the fuel pin elongation as the result of the potential cladding-fuel local interaction caused by the pellets displacement and/or skewing using the fuel jamming simulation. The paper proposes the following problem definition:

- the fuel pellet jamming can be defined as taking place from fuel lower end up to a certain core axial coordinate (jamming is assumed to take place along the entire core height);
- the cladding and fuel interact in each calculated layer along the core through the axial force that defines the same axial deformation increase both for the cladding and fuel for the time during which the jamming condition is satisfied.

Integral condition for the axial equilibrium of the cladding radial section:

$$\int_{R_{clad_in}}^{R_{clad_out}} \dot{\sigma}_z \cdot r \cdot dr + g_0 - \frac{\dot{F}_{ax}}{2\pi} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$g_0 = \frac{\dot{P}_{out} \cdot R_{clad_out}^2 - \dot{P}_{gap} \cdot R_{clad_in}^2}{2} \quad (2)$$

Integral condition of fuel radial section axial equilibrium:

$$\int_{R_{fuel_in}}^{R_{fuel_out}} \dot{\sigma}_z^* r dr + g_0^* + \frac{\dot{F}_{ax}}{2\pi} = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$g_0^* = \dot{P}_{gap} \frac{R_{fuel_out}^2}{2} - \dot{P}_{in} \frac{R_{fuel_in}^2}{2} \quad (4)$$

Here, \dot{F}_{ax} is the change rate of the axial force that acts on cladding and fuel provided that there is no contact between fuel and cladding, and the axial deformation rate of cladding and fuel is the same. R_{fuel_in} , R_{fuel_out} are respectively the inner radius and the outer radius of the inner cylinder. R_{clad_in} , R_{clad_out} are respectively the inner radius and the outer radius of the outer cylinder. \dot{P}_{in} , \dot{P}_{gap} , \dot{P}_{out} are the rates of the pressure change respectively on the inner cylinder inside, between the cylinders and the outer cylinder outside; $\dot{\sigma}_z$, $\dot{\sigma}_z^*$ are the rates of the axial stress change on cladding and fuel respectively.

The DRAKON code solves a system of equations to find the SSS (stress-strain state) parameters written in the rates of desired parameters, so the integral equilibrium conditions are presented in rates as well.

The algorithm used in the code to simulate the fuel pin operation and calculate the SSS parameters assumes in this case that \dot{F}_{ax} is determined from the solution of the system of equations for the cladding, and $\dot{\epsilon}_x$ (axial deformation rate) is determined from the solution of the system of equations for fuel. This is followed by an iterative process which proceeds until reproducibility of the calculation results with the accuracy specified is achieved.

Verification of the fuel pellets and cladding joint jamming model as compared with the analytical solution

In order to demonstrate that the algorithm of the cladding-fuel interaction through the axial force due to fuel pellet jamming is correct, the paper presents a test calculation of the SSS for two cylinders (the inner cylinder represents fuel, and the outer one represents the cladding) with the inner cylinder jamming (fuel) and a comparison with the analytical solution when the axial force that acts on the cylinders is defined as the input value. Initially, a calculation is done with simulation of the inner cylinder jamming. As a result, we obtain the axial force, F_{ax} , that acts on the cladding and the inner cylinder. The next calculation (with no jamming) uses the value of the axial force, F_{ax} , found in the problem with jamming (applied to the upper ends of the cylinders). The two numerical solutions are compared with each other and with the analytical solution.

Definition of the problem having an analytical solution (Timoshenko 1965; Lurie 1970): a long hollow thick-walled cylinder with bottoms is considered in inhomogeneous temperature field under the action of internal and external pressures; plane deformation, axisymmetric loading (Fig. 1). The axial force, F_{ax} , defined and applied to the cylinder's upper end affects the value of the normal stress, σ_z , distributed uniformly over the end.

Cylinder geometry:

$R_{fuel\ in} = 0$ mm; $R_{fuel\ out} = 4.25$ mm are the inner radius and the outer radius of the internal cylinder;

$R_{clad\ in} = 4.35$ mm; $R_{clad\ out} = 4.85$ mm are the inner radius and the outer radius of the cladding.

Pressure:

$P_1 = 0$ kg/mm² is the pressure inside the inner cylinder;

$P_2 = 0$ kg/mm² is the pressure on the inner cylinder's outside;

$P_3 = 10$ kg/mm² is the pressure on the outer cylinder's outside.

Figure 1. Calculation model.

Assumptions for both cylinders: the thermal expansion coefficient is $\alpha = 0$ (1/K), the Poisson modulus is $\mu = 0.3$; the elasticity modulus is $E = 260$ GPa.

We determine the axial force that acts on the upper ends of the cylinders from the DRAKON code solution of the problem with cylinders jamming under the action of the pressure on the outer cylinder's (cladding) outside. In this case, we obtain that $F_{ax} = 235.94$ kgf. The next step is the inner and outer cylinders SSS calculation without jamming, but taking into account the axial force that acts on the cylinders.

The solid line in Fig. 2 presents the analytical solution for the problem to determine the SSS of the cylinder under pressure, taking into account the action of the axial force; the symbols (points) show the DRAKON code solution for the test problem in two definitions (with jamming and without jamming taking into account the action of the given axial force $F_{ax} = 235.94$ kgf). The obtained solutions coincide with each other and with the analytical solution.

Model verification based on pie data of experimental BN-600 EFA-11 fuel assembly

An EFA-11 experimental fuel assembly with fuel pins of the BREST-OD-300 reactor type with the cladding made on EP823-Sh ferritic-martensitic steel and mixed nitride fuel was irradiated in the BN-600 reactor up to the maximum burnup of 9 at.% and the maximum damage dose of 107.6 dpa (Adamov et al. 2022).

The calculations took into account the fuel-cladding interaction along the core height via the axial force even if there is a gap between fuel and the cladding (jamming model).

Pellet jamming throughout the core height is assumed to take place at the reactor power increase and continues further for time Δt_{rel} . The symbols in Fig. 3 show the cladding and fuel column elongations at the end of lifetime depending on Δt_{rel} as specified for the calculation. The cladding elongation for the jamming mode persists throughout the whole refueling cycle prior to unloading was about 12 mm. That is, the possible cladding elongation is 3 to 12 mm depending on the jamming mode. The results of calculations with $\Delta t_{rel} = 500$ h and $\Delta t_{rel} = 1000$ h are close to the average elongation values (in accordance with the PIE results).

Fig. 4 presents the dynamics of fuel and cladding length change for the lifetime at $\Delta t_{rel} = 500$ h after the reactor power rise and for the calculation with jamming prior to the power decrease at refuelings.

Fig. 5 shows the circumferential cladding stresses (Fig. 5A, B) and the cladding and fuel axial stresses (Fig. 5C, D) along the core height some 500 h after the reactor power rise before ($t = 4447.04$ h) and right after ($t = 4459.08$ h) the jamming mode is canceled for the calculation option with $\Delta t_{rel} = 500$ h.

Figure 2. Calculation results for the test problem with fuel jamming, with external axial force without jamming and the analytical solution. The symbols (points) represent the DRAKON code solution.

Figure 3. Cladding and fuel column elongation depending on Δt_{rel} used in the calculation.

Figure 4. Dynamics of the fuel column and cladding length change. **A.** Jamming as the reactor power rise+ 500 h; **B.** jamming prior to power setback; blue continuous line – cladding; red dashed line – fuel.

Figure 5. Axial distribution of circumferential and axial stresses ~ 500 h after the reactor rise to power before and after the jamming mode is canceled.

Fig. 6 shows the calculated curves and PIE results (symbols) for the cladding and fuel column diameters.

For the calculation option with $\Delta t_{rel} = 500$ h, Fig. 7 shows the maximum along the core height ratio of the calculated stress intensity, σ_i , to the ultimate strength taking into account safety factor ($R_m^T/1.5$) in accordance with the static strength criterion (Likhachev and Pupko 1975) (Fig. 7A); its corresponding core height coordinate (Fig. 7B). Here $\sigma_i = \sqrt{(\sigma_\theta - \sigma_z)^2 + (\sigma_\theta - \sigma_r)^2 + (\sigma_r - \sigma_z)^2}$, where $\sigma_\theta, \sigma_z, \sigma_r$ are the principal stresses in the cylindrical system of coordinates.

Conclusions

A model of the fuel pellet jamming is proposed to describe the potential local interaction of dense nitride fuel with the cladding of fast reactor fuel pin. The model assumes that the cladding and fuel interact through the axial force. The axial force is determined from the condition of cladding and fuel radial section equilibrium and ensures that the jamming condition is satisfied (the same axial deformation increase). The presented model version assumes that jamming takes place throughout the core height.

Figure 6. Calculated curves and PIE results for the cladding and fuel column diameters.

Figure 7. Core height maximum ratio ($\sigma_i / (R_m^T / 1.5)$) versus time and its corresponding core height coordinate.

The model of joint jamming of fuel pellets was verified using the example of the SSS calculation for two cylinders (the inner cylinder representing fuel, and the outer cylinder representing the cladding) with the inner cylinder ("fuel") jamming.

The presented results of the jamming model verification based on the PIE results for the experimental BN-600

EFA-11 fuel assembly show that the model allows reproducing the fuel cladding elongation value. When the proposed model is used, the possible cladding elongation is from 3 to 12 mm, depending on the jamming mode duration. This range covers the experimental elongation data scatter range (from 3.5 mm to 10.8 mm) for the eighteen investigated fuel pins of EFA-11.

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